

Average yield of Ergene under flooded irrigation conditions (2000 mm water application) was about 6 t ha⁻¹. With the B3 treatment (1172 mm water application), yield was 4.7 t ha⁻¹.

Sprinkler irrigation can be thus used to increase WUE in conditions where water is scarce. Extra investment is, however, needed to install and operate the system. ■

Yield of rice under sprinkler irrigation. Edirne, Turkey. 1991-93.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)				Water applied (mm)				Water use efficiency (kg ha ⁻¹ mm ⁻¹)				
	1991	1992	1993	Mean	1991	1992	1993	Mean	1991	1992	1993	Mean	
4 d	A1B1	2.7 d	1.8 b	2.2 c	2.3 c	641	681	804	709	4.4	2.7	2.7	3.2
	A1B2	5.5 ab	3.2 abc	3.2 b	3.9 b	874	944	1004	940	6.3	3.3	3.1	4.2
	A1B3	5.9 a	3.6 ab	4.8 a	4.7 a	1107	1206	1203	1172	5.3	3.0	4.0	4.0
8 d	A2B1	3.7 cd	1.6 c	2.4 bc	2.5 c	641	681	804	709	5.7	2.3	2.9	3.6
	A2B2	4.6 bc	3.5 ab	4.4 a	4.2 ab	874	944	1004	940	5.3	3.7	4.4	4.4
	A2B3	4.8 ab	4.4 a	4.8 a	4.7 a	1107	1206	1203	1172	4.4	3.6	3.9	4.0
<i>F values</i>													
A	0.87	0.35	14.62	0.43									
B	24.36** ^b	9.28**	49.67**	52.59**									
A×B	4.18	0.50	3.77	0.32									
CD (0.05)	1.07	1.76	0.82	0.66									
CV (%)		12.49	18.06	12.03	16.55								

^aA: Irrigation interval: A1 = 4 d; A2 = 8 d. B: Irrigation depth (amount): B1 = same as pan evaporation; B2 = 50% of pan evaporation, B3 = 100% of pan evaporation. ^b** = significant at 1% level.

Farming systems

Effect of different rice cultures on crop yield in rice-based systems

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We investigated the performance of three rice cultures—(i) irrigated lowland (IL, rice seedlings transplanted in puddled soil under irrigated conditions); (ii) rainfed lowland (RL, crop established by dry seeding, followed by wet tillage at the 3-4 leaf stage under rainfed conditions [locally called halod]); and (iii) rainfed upland rice (DSR, rice dry seeded and raised as an upland crop under rainfed conditions)—and their subsequent effects on the yield of the

following upland crops of wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), linseed (*Linum usitatissimum*), and raya (*Brassica juncea*).

We conducted this experiment at the HPAU experimental farm in Palampur (32°6'N, 76°3'E, 1300 m altitude) during the 1993 and 1994 wet seasons. Soil was silty clay loam (Typic Hapludalf). Plots (5 × 3 m) were arranged in randomized complete block design with nine replications for rice and three replications for each upland crop. All crops received fertilizers at the recommended rates.

In both years, rice grain yield followed this trend: IL > RL > DSR. The differences were statistically significant. Grain yield of wheat and raya were highest in DSR and lowest in IL plots; linseed yield was not affected by the land preparation technique

adopted in the preceding rice crop.

The energy required to prepare the land after rice harvest was significantly affected by the land preparation technique used in rice. Puddling is the most intensive tillage practice in rice, followed by halod and dry tillage. Manual land preparation with the use of spades required about 967 h ha⁻¹ in IL, 633 h ha⁻¹ in RL, and 483 h ha⁻¹ in DSR. Considering that the energy of an adult worker equals 1.96 MJ human h⁻¹, land preparation after IL, RL, and DSR required 1895, 1241, and 947 MJ ha⁻¹, respectively. Thus, the energy required to prepare the seedbed after RL rice was about 2/3, and the energy needed for the crop after DSR was about 1/2 that of IL rice.

Rice in silty clay loam soil performed best under lowland irrigated conditions. But this rice culture did not favor the following crops of wheat and raya. They performed best after DSR. Linseed was unaffected by rice culture. Because wheat is next to rice in importance, appropriate tillage technology has to be developed to maximize crop yields in rice - wheat cropping systems. ■

Grain yield of crops (t ha⁻¹) in rice-based cropping systems involving three rice cultures.

Rice culture	Rice		Wheat		Linseed		Raya	
	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992
Irrigated lowland	4.2	4.5	3.0	3.3	1.2	1.3	0.9	1.0
Rainfed lowland	3.3	3.5	3.6	3.9	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.4
Direct seeded rice	2.9	3.1	3.9	4.1	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.7
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	ns	ns	0.1	0.2